

Cruise Report for AE2504 on R/V *Atlantic Explorer*

March 9-22, 2025

Bermuda to Woods Hole MA

Elizabeth B. Kujawinski

with contributions from science party

Acknowledgements

The activities of this cruise would not have been possible without the efforts of many individuals. First and foremost, we thank the National Science Foundation which funded the cruise through the Science & Technology Center grant for the Chemical Currencies of a Microbial Planet (Award #2019589). Secondly, we thank the captain and crew of the RV *Atlantic Explorer*, who provided a great platform for living and for doing science during our cruise. Lastly, we thank the C-CoMP staff, especially Laura Gray, the PIs, and the research groups whose efforts back on land made the sampling efforts successful.

Photo (front): The science party of AE2504. Front row (left to right): Arianna Krinos, Claire Garfield, Natalie Graham, Rachel Sandquist, Erin Maybach, Liz Kujawinski. Second row: Fadime Stemmer, Daniella Asturias, McKenzie Powers, Annika Gomez, Emily Hu. Back row: John “Chip” Breier, Matt McIlvin, Loay Jabre, Mike Jakuba, Ben Acosta, Sonya Dyrman. (taken by Max Unterberger, BIOS).

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Cruise summary

Overview

The goal of the cruise was to compare the microbial dynamics and processes in an oligotrophic region with a more productive region. This cruise is one of two planned with the same purpose, but to compare the same regions under bloom conditions (spring) with more stratified and nutrient-poor conditions (late summer). We chose two stations: the Bermuda Atlantic Time-series Study site (BATS) near Bermuda and the southernmost station of the New England Shelf Long-Term Ecological Research (NES-LTER station L11) site west of Connecticut (Figure 1). At each station, we conducted diel sampling near the surface (15m) and placed these samples into context with hydrographic profiles, underway samples, targeted incubations, and large-volume samples from CLIO. We sampled each region within an Lagrangian context, enabled by an SVP drifter deployed in each location.

Our field plans were interrupted by three storms, with 30-40 kt winds and 10-20 ft seas. Due to weather delays, we could not stop to sample along our transect between BATS and NES-LTER-L11. Nevertheless, we were able to accomplish the core mission of AE2504.

Station activities

We conducted a hydrographic profile at the start of each station's activities. This profile provided a snapshot of the physical, chemical, and biological dynamics of the upper 250 m. Prior to starting our diel sampling, we deployed an SVP drifter, which transmitted its position hourly. By sampling within 1km of the drifter's position, we maintained a Lagrangian transect, allowing us to stay nearly within the same water mass throughout the sampling scheme. The drifter followed the water mass at 20m, while we sampled the water column at 15m. However, the mixed layer was always >40 m, so the drifter and our samples occurred within the same water mass. We deployed the CTD-Niskin rosette every 4 hours for approximately 72 hrs. From each diel time-point, we collected meta-transcriptomics samples, dissolved and particulate metabolomics, bacterial production and respiration, particulate organic carbon, nutrients, and total (and dissolved) organic carbon. We complemented these samples with meta-proteomics samples collected from the underway system (sampled at 2m depth) and with meta-genomics samples collected from CLIO (at 15m). We did not get 72 continuous hours at either station due to weather.

To complement the field measurements, we conducted incubations using metabolite mixes from model axenic phytoplankton (Zhu, Anderson, in prep). One set of incubations probed the response of the microbial community to these mixes through metabolite uptake measurements, bacterial meta-transcriptomics, and community meta-genomics. Another set of incubations measured oxygen drawdown of the community to calculate respiratory quotients for different metabolites. At BATS, we examined the response of two heterotrophic bacteria, *Ruegeria pomeroyi* and *Alteromonas macleodii*, to surface seawater using bacterial invasion experiments (similar to Nowinski and Moran, 2021).

At each station, we deployed the CLIO autonomous sampling vehicle to collect large-volume samples for meta-proteomics and meta-genomics. In addition, we collected water for phytoplankton and bacterial isolation, and for phytoplankton community identification.

Station characteristics

BATS. We occupied the BATS site (31° 50'N, 64° 10'W) starting on Monday March 10, 2025. As is typical for the spring, the mixed layer was relatively deep (40-100m) and variable over the day. The sea surface temperature was approximately 20°C and the surface chlorophyll fluorescence was approximately 0.5 units. The subsurface chlorophyll maximum ranged between 40 m and 80 m, depending on the sea-state and mixed layer. We had a storm in the middle of our time at BATS which interrupted our diel observations and delayed the deployment of CLIO. However, prior to the storm's arrival, we collected water for the incubation experiment. The first 12 hr of that experiment were the most intensive and we completed those time-points prior to the resumption of CTD casts. Once the storm receded, we returned to the water mass indicated by the SVP drifter, and resumed our diel observations. In this second phase, we completed 24 hr of hourly CTD casts to assess the metabolite concentrations at 15 m on that time-scale. CLIO was deployed and recovered as it fit within that time-frame. We had to give up two time-points in the hourly casts, but none of the diel (4 hr) time points were affected. We completed two CLIO dives at BATS.

LTER. We arrived at L11 (39° 46'N, 70° 53'W) of the NES-LTER line on Tuesday March 18. The environment was very different from BATS (Figure 2). The sea surface temperature was much lower (~5-10°C), and the fluorescence was much higher (~2.5 units). Satellite photos taken with the PACE instrument suggested that we were in the midst of an intense spring bloom of *Coscinodiscus* (identified with the PlanktoScope by L. Jabre). Transmissometer readings were highly variable, likely due to the diatom's large size and high abundance, leading to significant backscatter interference. We started our science operations about 24 hr after arriving on site due to a storm. Once the winds receded, we conducted an overview hydrocast, followed by the initiation of our diel

observations (a CTD cast every 4 hrs). At approximately 1000, we collected water for the incubation experiment. On the second day of the diel experiment, we moved to hourly CTD casts and interspersed two CLIO dives. We concluded the diel observations at approximately 2100 and began our transit to Woods Hole MA.

We arrived at Woods Hole approximately 24 hr early to avoid our 4th storm of the cruise.

Figure 1. Final cruise trajectory showing sea surface temperature and chlorophyll concentrations along the cruise track. Figure created by Arianna Krinos.

Sample equipment

The CTD rosette was provided by the BIOS Science Support

Group and was prepared for initial deployment by marine technicians on our cruise, Emily Tate (lead), Max Unterberger, and Vlad Petrusevich (trainee) using the same set-up, sensors, and configurations as is used for the Bermuda Atlantic Time-Series Study CTD casts (see Methods from Johnson et al. 2025 for a complete description of the CTD configuration, sensors, and sampling method). The system was a SBE911+ CTD coupled with a variety of sensors and the SBE 32 Carousel Water Sampler. The sensors included: an internal Digiquartz pressure sensor, a Sea-Bird SBE-3F temperature sensor, a Sea-Bird SBE-4 conductivity cell, the Sea-Brid SBE-43 dissolved oxygen sensor, the WET Labs C-Star or Chelsea/Seatech Transmissometer, the Chelsea Aqua 3 Fluorometer, and the Biospherical/Licor PAR/Irradiance sensor. The rosette frame held 24, 12-L Niskin bottles. For planning purposes, we assumed an 11-L capacity because the Niskins rarely delivered 12 full liters.

We focused our operations on the surface ocean. Every overview hydrocast was deployed to 500m

Figure 2. Changes in air temperature, chlorophyll, water temperature, and wind speed along the cruise track of AE2504. Figure created by Arianna Krinos.

to get an overview of the water column for CLIO operations; every diel hydrocast was deployed to 150m to track the evolution of the deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM); and every hourly hydrocast was deployed to 50m to minimize deployment time.

We used the underway seawater intake system on the *AE* to collect large volume samples for metaproteomics at each major station and for metaproteomics and metagenomics during the transit between stations. This system brings in water at approximately 2m below the surface at the bow of the ship and records sea surface temperature, salinity, and fluorescence. We used the tap in the AFT lab exclusively to maintain sufficient pressure in the line.

Participants and parameters

List of participants with institutions

Elizabeth Kujawinski, PI, Chief Scientist	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Sonya Dyhrman, co-Chief Scientist	Columbia University
Benjamin Acosta, graduate student	Columbia University
Daniella Asturias, B2P fellow	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Chip Breier, faculty	University of Texas Rio Grande Valley
Claire Garfield, graduate student	University of Georgia
Annika Gomez, postdoc	Columbia University
Natalie Graham, B2P fellow	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Emily Hu, B2P fellow	Brown University
Loay Jabre, postdoc	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Mike Jakuba, engineer	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Arianna Krinos, C-CoMP postdoc	Brown University
Erin Maybach, graduate student	Columbia University
Matt McIlvin, research associate	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
McKenzie Powers, graduate student	University of Georgia
Rachel Sandquist, graduate student	University of California Santa Barbara
Fadime Stemmer, graduate student	MIT/WHOI

List of parameters and responsible parties

CORE OCEANOGRAPHY

Carbonate chemistry	B. Acosta, Hurley Lab
	Bates Lab
Chlorophyll and pigments	Bates Lab
Nutrients	Kujawinski Lab
TOC / DOC	Kujawinski Lab
Sampling location (SVP drifter)	Freilich Lab

CARBON

POC	Bates Lab
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BIOLOGY

Bacterial abundance	Moran Lab
Bacterial production	R. Sandquist, Carlson Lab
Bacterial isolation and cultivation	D. Asturias, Saito Lab
Community metagenomics (CLIO)	Meren Lab
Community metagenomics (Underway)	A. Krinos, Freilich Lab
Bacterial metatranscriptomics	Moran Lab
Eukaryotic metatranscriptomics	Dyhrman Lab
Metabolomics (dissolved and particulate)	Kujawinski Lab
Meta-Proteomics (CLIO and Underway)	L. Jabre, Saito Lab
Phytoplankton identification and abundance	L. Jabre, Saito Lab
Phytoplankton and viral isolation	A. Gomez, Dyhrman Lab
Protease activities	F. Stemmer, Saito Lab
Respiration by RSG	C. Garfield, Moran Lab
Respiration by O ₂ drawdown	R. Sandquist, Carlson Lab

INCUBATIONS

Metabolite uptake rates	Moran and Kujawinski Labs
Bacterial response to metabolite mixes	Moran and Carlson Labs
Microbial community shifts with metabolite additions	Dyhrman Lab
Invasion experiments with <i>R. pomeroyi</i> and <i>A. macleodii</i>	M. Powers, Moran Lab

Field observations and sampling modalities

Overall data management

We used an electronic log system (ELOG) to record all events on AE2504. The system was maintained on the internal *AE* network by the SSSG technicians. Instruments were identified prior to the cruise and events associated with each were pre-assigned. For example, the CTD instrument had five possible events: “deploy”, “maxDepth”, “recover”, “abort” and “other”. Each cruise participant could log an event for any instrument and the ship’s position (lat/long), date and time and the bottom depth were automatically recorded from the ship’s computers. All computers or tablets on the internal *AE* network could access ELOG, allowing for real-time event entry, although it was critical to ensure that these devices were not connected to institutional networks (like WHOI’s VPN). The ELOG system will facilitate data integration across research groups and will guide incorporation of data from our cruise into BCO-DMO and R2R databases, as required by NSF. The ELOG system is supplemented with written rosette log-sheets (digitized by photocopy), individual log sheets for major sampling efforts, and notes in individual lab notebooks.

Hydrography overview casts

The purpose of the overview casts was to map the water column’s physical and chemical characteristics to put our diel sampling into context and to plan the depths for the CLIO dives. We had one good hydrocast for each station: Cast 43 for BATS and Cast 45 for LTER. We sampled 8 depths: 5m, 15m, 40m, the DCM (nominally 70m), 90m, 120m, 200m and 500m. Nutrients, POC, phytoplankton pigments, cell abundance (via flow cytometry), bacterial production (via 3H-leucine incorporation), and TOC/DOC were sampled at each depth. Metabolites were sampled at 15m, 40m, the DCM, 90m, 120m, and 200m. DIC and Total Alkalinity were sampled at 5m, 15m, 40m, the DCM, and 500m. Microbial community composition samples (via 16S and 18S rDNA) were collected at 5m, 15m, the DCM, 200m and 500m. Triplicate MetaT samples were collected at 15m only.

Table 1. Parameters and sample numbers from each hydrographic cast. Table includes total number of samples collected from all casts including cast 1*.

Parameter	# samples BATS	# samples LTER	Responsible lab
Nutrients	45	15	Kujawinski
Particulate Organic Carbon (POC)	8	8	Bates
Phytoplankton pigments	8	7	Bates
Cell abundance	24	21	Moran
Bacterial production	129	39	Carlson
Total (and dissolved organic carbon)	48	24	Kujawinski
Metabolites	104	39	Kujawinski
DIC/TA	19	15	Bates
16S & 18S rDNA	36	20	Freilich
Eukaryotic MetaT	28	12	Dyrman

*16S/18S (pending success of DNA extractions) and cell abundance samples are the only samples that will be analyzed from cast 1. Rachel S. also has a water column profile of production from cast 1 that looks very similar to cast 43 (BATS hydrocast at the end of the time at BATS).

Lagrangian sampling: the SVP Drifters

Two 14" SVP Drifters (Pacific Gyre, Oceanside, CA, USA) were deployed and used to track water masses at 15 m during diel sampling efforts at BATS and LTER stations so that the same water mass could be sampled overtime using a Lagrangian approach. The configuration and set-up of the SVP drifters were as follows: no six pack compression, drogue ON/OFF Sensor, no deployment status sensor, no water temperature sensor, no air pressure sensor, non-replaceable battery, 6-spoke drogue, six section drogue, fixed tether (length: standard GDP), no flasher, sampling period: 1 hour sampling. Additional sensors were not added to the drifters because they were only being used to track water movement at 15m, but we may consider adding sea surface temperature sensors in the future to encourage adoption of the drifters into the Global Drifter Program.

Figure 3. Daniella Asturias (left) and Emily Hu (right) work on establishing the drifter signal at BIOS prior to the cruise. Photo taken by Arianna Krinos.

The drifters were tested to ensure that the telemetry signal was detected. To do this, the drifter was placed outside with no obstructions surrounding it (Figure 3). Notably, SVP drifters were delivered ready to test without any additional assembly. The outer plastic cover was removed, while taking care to ensure the paper tape and parts securing the tether and drogue remained intact. Telemetry services were activated through the Pacific Gyre web dashboard and a pull-pin magnet was removed to turn on the transmitter.

Telemetry service for WHOI_LG-SVP-0003 (Comms ID: 300534067527830) was

activated on March 7th at 13:35 UTC. It took about ~31 minutes after activation for the telemetry to lock onto the drifter position. The weather was partially cloudy. Telemetry was activated for WHOI_LG-SVP-0002 (Comms ID: 300534067526900) on March 7th at 12:20 UTC. The activation request took longer (the previous drifter took only 1-2 minutes to activate) completing after about ~24 minutes after the magnet had been taken out. Due to time constraints, the magnet was replaced to put it back into low battery mode. The drifter was tested again on March 8th at 13:16 UTC and took about ~ 2 hours 44 minutes to lock onto the drifter position. After testing, the drifters were left activated (magnet out and telemetry activated) until deployment. Throughout testing, care was taken to ensure that the drifter was not dropped, since the shock of the drop could dislodge or tamper the drifter.

The first drifter (WHOI_LG-SVP-0002) was deployed at the BATS station on March 10th ~ 30 min before the first diel cast (Cast 02). The drifter was left on the deck with no obstructions (and

somewhere it could remain dry as water would dissolve the paper parts holding it together) about an hour prior to deployment and the telemetry signal was acquired at the time of deployment. The ship was directed to proceed dead-ahead into the wind and the drifter was deployed from the main deck at the stern. Telemetry services were deactivated on March 16th after 139 total hours. The second drifter (WHOI_LG-SVP-0003) was deployed at the LTER station on March 19th 5 minutes before the first hydrocast at this station (Cast 45) due to storm conditions (Figure 4). The telemetry signal was acquired an hour after deployment. The same deployment strategy as the first drifter was used. Telemetry services for this drifter were deactivated on March 25th after 154 total hours.

Figure 4. Emily Hu (left), Natalie Graham (right), and Emily Tate (behind) prepare the drifter for deployment at the NES-LTER station (left). From the left, Emily Tate, Emily Hu, and Natalie Graham deploy the SVP drifter at the NES-LTER station (right). Photos taken by Arianna Krinos.

Figure 5. Drifter positions (blue crosses) at each hourly ping from the instrument at the BATS station (left) and the NES-LTER station (right). Points show the position of the ship within one hour of the sampling time as the vessel moved as close as possible to the current SVP position. Points indicating ship positions are colored by the primary chlorophyll measurement in $\mu\text{g/L}$ from the underway system at that time. Black line segments indicate vessel trajectory between original ship position and drifter position during sampling. Figure by Arianna Krinos.

Large-volume sampling: CLIO

CLIO operations

We conducted four CLIO dives, detailed in Appendix 1.

CLIO samples

We conducted a total of four CLIO dives, one of which failed and three yielded viable samples (see CLIO report for details).

Omics sampling. On the first successful dive (clio051), omics samples were collected at 15(x2), 20, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90 and 120 m. These depths were chosen to sample above, within, and below the chl-a maximum at high resolution, and to sample at the same depth as the CTD (15m). On the second successful dive (clio052), omics samples were collected at 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 500, 1000, and 1500m. This dive was used to sample microbial communities deeper in the water column in addition to the surface. On the third successful dive (clio054), omics samples were collected at 5, 15(x2), 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, and 100m. These depths were chosen to sample above, within, and below the chl-a maximum, and to take samples at the same depth as the CTD (15m).

After each successful dive, filters were sliced and distributed as follows: $\frac{1}{2}$ for proteomics, $\frac{1}{4}$ for DNA, $\frac{1}{8}$ for protease assay and bacterial isolations, $\frac{1}{8}$ for 'archive'. Filter slicing and packaging was done as quickly as possible and using frozen cryovial racks when possible. DNA samples were flash frozen in liquid nitrogen before being stored in the -80 freezer, protein and archival samples were

placed directly in the -80 freezer. All samples from CLIO are currently stored in Saito Lab freezers at WHOI.

Note: Only one filtration stack (Tigerclaw) functioned properly during the cruise, so we were limited on the number of samples we managed to collect. As such, we did not collect any GFF samples on CLIO.

New metabolomics sampler. On the second CLIO dive, we tested a new dissolved metabolomics sampler (Figure 6). The overall plan was to collect whole water into a sample bag stored within an in-situ incubation chamber. Water was pumped through (Tigerclaw) at 30m into a 3L bag (FlexFoil PLUS Sample Bag; Cat. No: 252-03). Prior to deployment, the incubation chamber was filled with freshwater. This water was displaced during pumping. Two bags were prepared but only one pump worked during the deployment and thus one sample was collected. When the sample came on deck, the bag was removed from the incubation chamber and stored at 4C until we arrived at WHOI. At WHOI, water was pumped from the bag through a 0.2-um Omnipore filter using the Luer-Lok connections and frozen. The filtrate will be processed in the same fashion as the PPL samples collected from the hydrocasts (see above).

Figure 6. Clio samplers on AE2504. On the left is the new metabolomics sampler, with bags inserted into incubation chambers. On the right is the filter stack. Photo by Daniella Asturias.

Large-volume sampling: Underway system

We used the ship's underway pump (intake at ~2 m depth) to sample for metaproteomics, metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, POC/PON and pigments. This was done as a complement to the diel sampling efforts at BATS and LTER, and as opportunistic sampling of the transit between the two stations. Overall, we were interested in these samples for examining spatial and temporal shifts in community and/or functional characteristics at the surface. Samples for metaP, metaG and metaT were collected on 142 mm Versapor filters (51 μm and 0.2 μm). Samples for POC/PON and pigments were collected on pre-combusted 142 mm GFFs. MetaP and GFF samples are currently stored in the Saito Lab freezers at WHOI. MetaP samples will be analyzed in the Saito Lab. MetaG and metaT samples were given to the Freilich group for storage and subsequent analysis.

At BATS, underway samples were collected hourly between April 11th and April 12th, and every 2-3 hours while on station for the rest of the time. During transit, samples were collected every two

hours. At LTER, we were busier with CLIO operations, so underway sampling was more sporadic. We still managed to sample every few hours. See Figure 7 for underway sampling map and Table 2 for underway sampling summary.

Sampling procedure:

Filters were placed inside a custom-made filter holder and connected directly to the ship’s underway faucet. The out-flow line (the filtrate) was connected to a flow meter to measure the volume of filtered water. Versapor filters were sliced into quarters and divided for metaP, metaG and metaP (and on some occasions, a small piece was used by Fadime for protease assay experiments). A metal punch was used to cut 25 diameter circles from the GFF filters (6-11 punches per filter). Protein and GFF samples were placed directly in the -80 freezer, DNA and RNA samples were flash frozen in liquid nitrogen before transfer to the -80 freezer.

Additional notes:

- We discovered halfway through the cruise that the ship had an additional diaphragm underway pump at ~2 m depth. A diaphragm pump is more gentle and less disruptive to microbial cells. We did not switch into using this pump to maintain consistency, but we recommend exploring this option in the future.
- Filters that had a lot of *Coscinodiscus sp.* biomass were patchy (uneven color on the filters), and the diatom biomass would move around as the filters were being sliced. It is therefore likely that different slices of the same filter had different amounts of biomass on them.

Table 2. Number and types of sampling events at BATS, during transit, and LTER. Note that several individual samples were usually collected for each sampling event (e.g. several slices per omics filter).

	Omics sampling events	GFF sampling events
BATS	73	9
Transit	40	7
LTER	9	1
Total	122	17

Figure 7. Map showing the cruise track (red dots), and locations at which underway samples were collected (open green triangles). Grayscale background color indicates bottom depth. Figure by Loay Jabre.

Observations and incubations tied to diel forcing

Diel Observations: Overview

The purpose of the diel observations at each station was to track the biological and chemical dynamics of the microbial community in the surface ocean over more than one day-night cycle. We chose 15m as the target depth for this field study, which was squarely within the mixed layer of both stations but was not likely to be affected by wind-driven changes at the sea surface. We repositioned the ship 30 min prior to each time point, based on the drifter position at the top of the hour. Every four hours, we collected samples for nutrients, TOC/DOC, POC, microbial abundance (by flow cytometry, FCM), bacterial single-cell respiration (via Redox Sensitive Green, RSG), intracellular and extracellular metabolites, and bacterial and eukaryotic meta-transcriptomics. At selected points over the 3-day effort, we collected bacterial production measurements and conducted “invasion” experiments with C-CoMP model heterotrophs *R. pomeroyi* and *A. macleodii*. Due to weather and associated delays, we could not acquire continuous samples, but we covered >48 hours for each station (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Overview of diel sampling casts (gray vertical dashed lines) and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) from the forward mast of the R/V Atlantic Explorer during the cruise (black points and lines). Figure by Arianna Krinos.

Diel Observations: General parameters

Nutrients:

At BATS, we collected triplicate nutrient samples directly from the Niskin. We did not wear gloves to avoid contamination from the nitrile gloves used for all other analyses. All nutrient samples were collected in 30mL HDPE bottles. Bottles were rinsed three times with water from the Niskin bottles, and then filled up to the neck. Samples were frozen at -20°C until offloading in Woods Hole. Samples will be analyzed by a third-party.

At the LTER station, we used the same sampling strategy except that samples were filtered through a $0.2\mu\text{m}$ Omnipore filter to remove large cells.

TOC/DOC:

At BATS, we only collected TOC samples due to the likelihood of contamination through filtration of these low abundance samples. Triplicate samples were collected directly from the Niskin into pre-combusted clear 40mL EPA vials with Teflon-lined septa. Vials were rinsed three times before sample collection. Samples were acidified to pH 2 with $40\mu\text{L}$ concentrated HCl and stored at 4°C until offloading in Woods Hole. Samples will be analyzed by the Carlson lab at UCSB.

At the LTER station, we collected both TOC and DOC samples. TOC samples were collected the same way as at the BATS station, while DOC samples were collected after filtration through a $0.2\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ Omnipore filter.

Bacterial abundance:

We collected samples for bacterial abundance by flow cytometry. Triplicate samples for diel timepoints and the hydrocasts at BATS and the LTER were fixed to a final concentration of 1% (v/v) paraformaldehyde, incubated at 4°C for 20 minutes, and stored at -80°C . Samples were analyzed at CTEGD Cytometry Shared Resource Laboratory at the University of Georgia where they were stained with DAPI ($1\mu\text{g/ml}$) and analyzed on an Agilent Quanteon flow cytometer (Acea,

Biosciences Inc, San Diego CA) with a 405 nm laser with a DAPI (445/45 nm) bandpass filter and chlorophyll a (695/40 nm) bandpass filters, and a 561 nm laser with phycoerythrin (586/20 nm) bandpass filter. Heterotrophic bacteria and *Prochlorococcus* were gated using DAPI fluorescence against chlorophyll fluorescence, *Synechococcus* was gated using phycoerythrin against chlorophyll, and other phytoplankton were gated using chlorophyll against forward scatter. Results from BATS are plotted in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Cell abundances (cells/ml) and standard deviation at BATS over the diel cycling period (n = 3). Gray indicates night sampling (06:00 to 18:00). Black indicates where CTD operations were suspended. Figure by Claire Garfield.

Particulate Organic Carbon (POC):

We collected 3L in HDPE bottles provided by the BATS program (R. Johnson). Samples were filtered through pre-combusted, pre-weighed glass fiber filters (25mm GF/F) as quickly as possible. Filters were removed from the inline holders and frozen at -20C. Samples will be analyzed by the Bates Lab at BIOS. Single samples were collected at every diel timepoint, and triplicates were collected once every 24hr period.

Bacterial Production: ³H-leucine incorporation

The primary goal of these incubations was to measure ³H-leucine incorporation rates in seawater samples to calculate the rate of organic carbon assimilation by bacterioplankton. From this data we hope to elucidate the connection between diel cycling of metabolites and bacterioplankton activity in the surface ocean at the BATS and LTER sample sites.

Sample collection and incubations

Approximately 30 minutes before sampling, a 10:1 ³H-leucine diluted stock was made for each cast from the concentrated stock. Next, 4 x 2 mL microcentrifuge tubes were prepared for every depth sampled. One of the tubes for each depth and/or cast was used as a killed control sample. 2 mL microcentrifuge tubes were also set up for specific activity checks (SA), with one SA for the diel timepoints and 3 SA for the depth profiles.

When the CTD was brought on deck, seawater samples were collected directly from the Niskin in 30mL PC bottles (acid washed, MiliQ rinsed, and triple sample rinsed). 1.6 ml of seawater sample was added in each BP tube, from PC tubes on non-rad counters across from the hood using a 5mL

pipette and tips. Seawater samples were then moved to the Rad bench and 100 µl concentrated trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added to the kill controls. 12 µL of the 3H leucine diluted stock was added to samples and the start time was recorded. Samples were mixed and 10 µl was taken at random and put into the specific activity checks. Water baths were prepared with Niskin water and in situ temperature was recorded before incubation of the samples in the dark for 2-4 hours. When sampling for multiple depths at multiple temperatures, water baths were made in 3°C temperature bins based on in situ temperatures measured on the CTD for each cast. After incubation, samples were killed with 100 µl TCA and the kill time was recorded. All samples were then vortexed and kept in the fridge until extraction.

Extractions

Centrifuge was cooled to 4°C and samples (both live and KC) were vortexed - SA are not extracted. Samples were spun for 7 minutes at 14000 rotations per minute and 4°C and then decanted into the bench top waste container with caution not to disrupt the pellet. 1.6ml 5% TCA was then added to each microtube and once again spun for 7 minutes at 14000 rotations per minute and 4°C and decanted. Next, 1.6ml 80% EtOH was then added to each microtube and once again spun for 7 minutes at 14000 rotations per minute and 4°C and decanted. Finally, 1.5ml Ultima Gold was added to each sample and each sample was vortexed. 1.5ml Ultima Gold was also added to the Specific Activities and they were vortexed. Samples and SA were left for at least 2 hrs at room temperature before being ran on the scintillation counter aboard the R/V Atlantic Explorer

Samples Collected

Parameter	# Samples BATS	# Samples LTER	Lab for Analysis
Bacterial Production (3H Leucine Incorporation)	129	39	Carlson

Table 3. Total Bacterial Production samples collected aboard AE2504.

Table 4. Breakdown of the number of bacterial production samples taken at each diel time point for each study site (excluding kill controls and specific activity checks).

	22:00					
BATS	3	3	6	12	6	3
LTER	3	3	3	3	3	0

Data Progress

All samples have been run and the data has been processed (Figure 10). Currently working on testing for significance and looking for trends within the diel cycle within and between the two study sites.

Figure 10. Preliminary bacterial production depth profiles at BATS and the LTER (a) and diel bacterial production trends. Asterisk denotes significant difference between the two timepoints within the diel cycle (b) prepared by Rachel Sandquist.

Bacterial respiration: RSG

To examine diel patterns in single cell respiration rates, we collected samples at BATS using the RedoxSensor Green method described in Munson-McGee et al. (2022). Briefly, we incubated the natural microbial community from bulk seawater with 1 μ L of RedoxSensorTM Green (Thermo Fisher Scientific), inverted gently several times, and incubated at 19.7 °C for 30 minutes. Samples preserved with cryopreservative (11x Tris-EDTA, 55% glycerol), incubated for one minute, and flash frozen in LN₂. Samples were stored at -80 °C and transported on dry ice for further processing. Dead-cell controls were generated by amending 1 ml of sample to a final concentration of 9% cryopreservative, flash frozen in LN₂, and stored at -80 °C. On shore, dead-cell controls were thawed and incubated in 10% (v/v) paraformaldehyde at 4 °C for approximately 27 hours. Samples were then incubated with 1 μ L RedoxSensorTM Green for 30 minutes at 4 °C, flash frozen in LN₂, and stored at -80 °C. Samples were sent to the University of Georgia for analysis by flow cytometry.

Diel Observations: Meta-Transcriptomics

To track diel oscillations of microbial gene expression, we collected samples for metatranscriptomic analysis from eukaryotic and prokaryotic communities. Eukaryotic signals were size fractionated to isolate larger eukaryote ($> 5 \mu\text{m}$) signals from picoeukaryote ($0.2 - 5 \mu\text{m}$) signals, while prokaryotic metatranscriptomics were collected from the smaller size fraction ($0.2 - 5 \mu\text{m}$).

At each diel time point, 60 liters of seawater were collected from the CTD for bacterial and eukaryotic metatranscriptomic sampling. Over each 24-hour period, samples were collected every 4 hours for a total of six time points per period: three during the night (collected at 2200, 0200, and 0600 hours) under red light, and three during the day (collected at 1000, 1400, and 1800 hours) under ambient light (Fig. 4). Seawater was collected into three 20 L carboys and processed using a peristaltic pump with two filtration lines per replicate (A,B,C) (Figure 11). Line 1 filtered seawater sequentially through a $5 \mu\text{m}$ polycarbonate (PC) filter and a secondary $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ polyethersulfone (PES) Sterivex filter, with the filtrate collected into a graduated carboy. Line 2 filtered seawater through only a $5 \mu\text{m}$ PC filter, and the resulting filtrate was collected separately. The $5 \mu\text{m}$ -filtered seawater from Line 2 was used as inflow for bacterial metatranscriptomic sampling. Approximately 15 liters of $5 \mu\text{m}$ -filtered water ($\sim 5 \text{ L}$ per carboy) were collected for bacterial metatranscriptomics at each time point. At the BATS site, a $200 \mu\text{m}$ nitex mesh pre-filter was attached to the intake line to exclude large particles from the samples. However, at the LTER site, the mesh pre-filter was omitted to allow the collection of larger diatom cells present in the water column. Following filtration, $5 \mu\text{m}$ filters were gently vacuumed to remove excess water and transferred into cryovials. For the $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ Sterivex filters, excess water was expelled using a syringe before sealing the filters with end caps and putty. All samples ($5 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ filters) were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored for the duration of the cruise. The average time from the start of filtration to flash freezing was approximately 50 minutes.

A total of 288 eukaryotic metatranscriptomic samples (189 BATS, 99 LTER) were collected over the diel experiments by members of the Dyrman Lab and transported back to the Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory (LDEO) in liquid nitrogen dewars. Upon arrival at LDEO the samples were transferred into long-term liquid nitrogen storage to await RNA extraction and sequencing by members of the Dyrman Lab. Upon transfer, we noticed 12 of the LTER Sterivex had lost their label and could not be identified. All LTER time points have at least one Sterivex remaining with the exception of the 20 hour and 24 hour time points. The $5 \mu\text{m}$ filters will be poly-A selected prior to sequencing in order to explicitly detect the functional, protein-coding activity in the messenger RNA (mRNA) of the eukaryotic population.

Bacterial metatranscriptomic samples were collected by filtering $\sim 4 \text{ L}$ of $5 \mu\text{m}$ -filtered water at BATS and 2 L of $5 \mu\text{m}$ -filtered water at the LTER through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ polyethersulfone (PES) membrane filter (Pall and Millipore). Samples were flash frozen in LN₂, transported on dry ice to the University of Georgia, and stored at $-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for further processing.

Figure 11. Eukaryotic metatranscriptomic sampling time points during **(left)** daylight (1000, 1400, and 1800 hours) and **(right)** night time (2000, 0200, 0600 hours). Photos taken by Erin Maybach.

Diel Observations: Metabolomics

We collected four types of metabolomics samples for future analysis. From each time-point, we collected approximately 4.5L of seawater in two 2.5L Teflon bottles which were rinsed three times with seawater from the Niskin rosette. We filtered each sample through an in-line 0.2- μ m Omnipore filter (Figure 12). The filtrate was collected in clean, rinsed, 2.5L Teflon bottles. In addition to the bottles, we collected triplicate 25mL samples in amber 40mL EPA vials for dissolved metabolite analysis via the benzoyl chloride derivatization method (Widner et al., 2021) and a single aliquot of ~30mL in a clear 40mL EPA vial for aniline derivatization (Halloran et al., in prep). All vials were combusted prior to the cruise. The volume of the filtrate was measured by ruler on board and the height of the filtrate was recorded. The total volume filtered was the amount collected in 2.5L Teflon bottles plus the volumes of the BC and aniline samples when at BATS. The total volume filtered also included nutrient and DOC samples once at the biologically active LTER station. The filters were removed from the filter holders, folded cell-side inward, and placed inside cryovials, prior to storage at -80°C prior to offloading in Woods Hole. BC and aniline samples were stored at -20°C until arrival in Woods Hole. Filtrate in the Teflon bottles was acidified to pH ~3 with concentrated HCl (approximately 2.5mL for 2.5L) and then extracted with PPL resin (Dittmar et al. 2008, with modifications from Longnecker 2015). PPL cartridges were eluted with methanol and stored at -20°C for dry-down and analysis in Woods Hole. The Kujawinski lab will analyze all metabolomics samples at WHOI.

Total number of samples: BATS intracellular + BATS PPL + BATS BC + BATS aniline = 290; LTER intracellular + LTER PPL + LTER BC + LTER aniline = 154

Figure 12. (left) On ship set up for PPL solid phase extraction. Displays the vacuum manifold, teflon tubing, and 2.5L teflon bottles used in sample collection. **(right)** On ship peristaltic pump set up for filtration. Photos taken by Natalie Graham.

Diel Observations: “Invasion” experiments (BATS)

Bacterial ‘invasion’ studies were conducted across a diel cycle at the BATS station using the model bacteria *R. pomeroyi* DSS-3 and *A. macleodii* MIT1002. These short-term bioassays are used to identify the metabolites available in seawater via the expression of transporter and catabolic genes in the invading bacterium (Nowinski and Moran 2021). The primary goal of the invasion studies at BATS was to characterize the presence of labile metabolites across a diel cycle in the oligotrophic North Atlantic Ocean, as seen by two copiotrophic bacteria with distinct metabolic strategies and substrate preferences.

A total of six invasion experiments were conducted at BATS across a diel cycle from March 11 to March 13th (see Table 5) using methods described in Nowinski and Moran (2021) with slight modifications (see Figure 13). Axenic cultures of *R. pomeroyi* and *A. macleodii* were prepared 38 hours before each invasion experiment. First, each bacterium was inoculated into ½ YTSS liquid medium and grown to stationary phase for 24 hours at 20°C. Each culture was transferred into fresh ½ YTSS

medium and incubated at 20°C until they reached late exponential phase (~14 hours). Cells were spun down once at 8,000 rpm for 3 minutes to remove rich medium and were resuspended in 0.22 µm filtered BATS seawater. Each bacterium was added into four replicate bottles containing 1-liter BATS whole seawater at a 1:1 ratio of invading bacterium cells to native bacterial cells. The mixtures were incubated in the dark at 20°C for 90 minutes. Each replicate bottle was filtered through a 2 µm polycarbonate filter followed by a 0.22 µm PES Sterivex filter to collect the bacterial fraction. Filters were immediately flash frozen in liquid nitrogen followed by storage at -80°C. Flow cytometry samples (1 ml fixed with 16% paraformaldehyde; 1% final concentration) were taken from BATS whole seawater, from each bacterial culture prior to being added into the seawater, and from the invasion incubation bottles at T-initial (0 minutes) and T-final (90 minutes). Two control experiments were conducted following the methods described above but *R. pomeroyi* and *A. macleodii* cultures were inoculated into L1 medium with either 10 mM glucose or no substrate.

There are a total of 210 flow cytometry samples, 64 bacterial RNA samples, and 46 eukaryotic RNA samples that were collected from the six invasion experiments (see Table 6). All samples collected during the invasion experiments will be processed and analyzed by M. Powers (Moran Lab). Flow cytometry samples will be run on the Agilent Quanteon analyzer at the University of Georgia Cytometry Shared Resource Laboratory in late April. Bacterial RNA samples will be extracted using a modified protocol developed by the Moran lab in early May. Library preparation and Illumina sequencing will be completed at the University of Georgia Genomics and Bioinformatics Core (GGBC) in May or early June. Eukaryotic RNA samples (2 µm filters) were collected from each invasion experiment but there are currently no plans to sequence or analyze.

Table 5. Invasion experiment metadata and number of samples collected.

Invasion Experiment	Date	Diel Time Point	Cast Number	FCM	Bacterial RNA	Euk RNA
1	March 11	2 PM	4	27	8	8
2	March 11	2 AM	7	27	8	8
3	March 11	6 AM	8	27	8	8
4	March 13	10 AM	15	27	8	8
5	March 13	6 PM	19	27	8	8
6	March 13	10 PM	23	27	8	8
Glucose control	April 16	-	-	24	8	-
No substrate control	April 16	-	-	24	8	-

Figure 13. Protocol for bacterial invasion experiments using the model marine bacteria *R. pomeroyi* DSS-3 and *A. macleodii* MIT1002 (four biological replicates per bacterium). Six bacterial invasion experiments using both bacteria were completed across a full diel cycle at BATS. Figure made by McKenzie Powers.

Table 6. Parameters and sample numbers from Diel casts.

Parameter	# samples BATS	# samples LTER	Responsible lab
Nutrients	66	33	Kujawinski
TOC/DOC	66	63	Kujawinski
Bacterial abundance	89	32	Moran
Particulate Organic Carbon (POC)	24	17	Bates
Bacterial respiration - RSG	76	0	Moran
16S & 18S rDNA	13	9	Freilich
Prokaryotic MetaT	60	33	Moran
Eukaryotic MetaT	189	87*	Dyhrman
Bacterial production	129	39	Carlson
Metabolites	290	154	Kujawinski

"Invasion" experiments - bacterial abundance	210	NA	Moran
"Invasion experiments" - bacterial RNA	64	NA	Moran
"Invasion experiments" - euk RNA	48	NA	Moran

*99 sterivex samples were collected at LTER but 12 were lost due to label failure. T4, T8, T16, T32, and T40 are missing one sample; T12, T20, and T28 are missing two samples; T24 is missing all three sterivex samples.

Incubations: Metabolite Drawdown

Experimental goal:

In this experiment, we aimed to measure the microbial community's response to metabolite mixtures designed based on culture data from Zhu & Anderson (in prep.). Two metabolite mixes were used: one based on metabolites released by *Prochlorococcus* and the other based on metabolites released by *Micromonas commoda* (Table 7).

We conducted two short-term incubation experiments lasting approximately 6 and 12 hours to assess metabolite drawdown and microbial activity. During each experiment, we collected samples for dissolved metabolite measurements to quantify assimilation rates (on a per-molecule basis). At the end of each incubation, metatranscriptomic samples were collected to assess shifts in gene expression across the microbial community.

In parallel, we conducted a long-term incubation to observe changes in the microbial gene pool composition in response to repeated metabolite additions. Long-term experiments at BATS and the LTER site lasted 96 and 72 hours, respectively, with recurring metabolite additions every 24 hours. At the conclusion of the long-term experiment, we harvested samples for metagenomic analysis to detect changes in the community's functional potential in response to the metabolite treatments.

Table 7. Final concentration for incubation amendments in μM carbon.

Compound	<i>Prochlorococcus marinus</i> (PM)	<i>Micromonas commoda</i> (MC)
Alanine	0.88	0.68
Aspartate	0.78	0.46
Glutamic Acid	3.68	1.17
Glycine	0.23	0
Isoleucine	0.94	0
Leucine	0.88	0.42
Lysine	0	0.40
Methionine	0.17	0
Phenylalanine	1.14	0.63
Proline	0.24	3.72
Taurine	0	1.53
Tyrosine	0	0.48
Valine	1.07	0.51

Experimental design:

Initial T0hr sampling and experimental setup

A total of 132 liters of seawater were collected from 15 m depth for the phytoplankton exometabolite incubation experiments. Seawater was collected in the morning (1000 hours at BATS; 0500 hours at LTER) to mimic the natural timing of morning carbon fluxes experienced by microbial communities. Initial measurements (T0hr) were taken directly from the CTD and included metatranscriptomes, metagenomes, flow cytometry (FCM), and RSG (BATS only) (see Methods). At this time, 18 replicate 5 L incubation bottles were filled through a 200 μm nitex pre-filter. Three concurrent experiments were initiated: a short-term incubation (6 hours), an intermediate incubation (12 hours), and a long-term incubation (multiple days). Each experiment included triplicate 5 L bottles spiked with synthetic dissolved organic carbon (DOC) pools derived from either *P. marinus* or *M. commoda* to a final concentration of 10 μM carbon (Table 3). Additionally, triplicate 1 L bottles of 0.2 μm -filtered (PTFE/Teflon) seawater were amended with 10 μM *P. marinus* DOC to serve as an abiotic control. Following DOC addition, initial metabolite samples were collected from each incubation bottle (see Methods).

Short-term and intermediate incubation experiments

For the short-term (6-hour) and intermediate (12-hour) incubations and the abiotic control, metabolite samples were collected every 3 hours to track drawdown. Metatranscriptomic samples were collected after 6 and 12 hours, respectively. FCM samples were also taken every 3 hours across all incubation types, including from the abiotic control at the T6hr and T12hr time points. RSG samples were collected at the T6hr time points from the short-term incubation bottles at BATS only (Figure 14).

Long-term incubation experiments

The long-term incubations lasted 97 hours at BATS and 73 hours at LTER. During the first 12 hours, FCM samples were collected every 3 hours alongside the short- and intermediate-term experiments. After the 24-hour mark (T24hr), each long-term incubation replicate was amended with an additional 1 mL of either *P. marinus* or *M. commoda* DOC mix. Before and after each DOC addition, metabolite samples were collected, and FCM samples were taken at each time point to monitor bacterial abundance. This amendment and sampling cycle was repeated every 24 hours thereafter. At the final time point (T97hr at BATS and T73hr at LTER), final metabolite and FCM samples were collected. All 5 L replicate bottles were then filtered for metagenomic analysis (Figure 14).

Methods

Metatranscriptomics

Metatranscriptome samples were taken by filtering ~ 5 L of 200- μm filtered water through a 0.2 μm PES membrane filter (Millipore) and flash-freezing in LN₂. Bacterial transcriptomics samples were sent to the University of Georgia on dry ice for downstream analysis.

Metagenomics

Seawater was filtered through triplicate filtration lines (A, B, C) using a peristaltic pump for metagenome sampling. Each triplicate line filtered approximately 5 L onto a 0.2 μm

polyethersulfone (PES) Sterivex filter, with the filtrate collected into a graduated carboy. Once filtering was complete, excess water was expelled from the filter containers using a syringe, and tubes were sealed with end caps and putty before being flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored for the duration of the cruise. The average time from the start of filtration to flash freezing was approximately 30 minutes. A total of 18 metagenomic samples (9 BATS, 9 LTER) were collected from the incubation experiments by members of the Dyhrman Lab and transported back to the Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory (LDEO) in liquid nitrogen dewars. Upon arrival at LDEO, the samples were transferred into long-term liquid nitrogen storage to await DNA extraction and sequencing by members of the Dyhrman Lab.

RSG samples

Bacterial respiration (RSG) samples were taken using the RedoxSensor Green method described in Munson-McGee et al. (2022). Briefly, we incubated the natural microbial community from bulk seawater with 1 μ l of RedoxSensor™ Green (Thermo Fisher Scientific), inverted gently several times, and incubated at 19.7 °C for 30 minutes. Samples preserved with cryopreservative (11x Tris-EDTA, 55% glycerol), incubated for one minute, and flash frozen in LN2. Samples were stored at -80 °C and transported on dry ice for further processing. Dead-cell controls were generated by amending 1 ml of sample to a final concentration of 9% cryopreservative, flash frozen in LN2, and stored at -80 °C. On shore, dead-cell controls were thawed and incubated in 10% (v/v) paraformaldehyde at 4 °C for approximately 27 hours. Samples were then incubated with 1 μ L RedoxSensor™ Green for 30 minutes at 4 °C, flash frozen in LN2, and stored at -80 °C. Samples were sent to the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences Single Cell Genomics Center and the University of Georgia for downstream analysis.

FCM samples

Triplicate samples were fixed to a final concentration of 1% (v/v%) paraformaldehyde, incubated at 4 °C for 20 minutes, and stored at -80 °C. Samples were analyzed at CTEGD Cytometry Shared Resource Laboratory at the University of Georgia where they were stained with DAPI (1 μ g/ml) and analyzed on an Agilent Quanteon flow cytometer (Acea, Biosciences Inc, San Diego CA) with a 405 nm laser with a DAPI (445/45 nm) bandpass filter and chlorophyll a (695/40 nm) bandpass filters, and a 561 nm laser with phycoerythrin (586/20 nm) bandpass filter. Heterotrophic bacteria and *Prochlorococcus* were gated using DAPI fluorescence against chlorophyll fluorescence, *Synechococcus* was gated using phycoerythrin against chlorophyll, and other phytoplankton were gated using chlorophyll against forward scatter (Figure 15).

Metabolite samples

Approximately 50-100 ml of incubation water was collected from each replicate bottle, resulting in biological replicates for each treatment. Samples were aliquoted into 125mL polycarbonate bottles before filtering. For extracellular profiles, the samples were filtered using teflon and an in-line 0.2- μ m Omnipore filter. Biological replicates were collected as 25 mL filtrate samples in pre-combusted amber 40 mL EPA vials for dissolved metabolite analysis via the benzoyl chloride derivatization method. Vials were rinsed with filtrate before collecting the full 25mL sample. Filtrate samples were stored at -20°C until arrival in Woods Hole. To understand intracellular profiles at predetermined time points of interest, filters were removed from the filter holders after each treatment group,

folded cell-side inward, and placed inside cryovials and stored at -80°C until arrival in Woods Hole. The Kujawinski lab will analyze all metabolomics samples at WHOI.

Figure 14. Experimental setup and sampling scheme for the phytoplankton exometabolite incubation experiments. Triplicate 5 L bottles spiked with *P. marinus* or *M. commoda* were sampled for each timepoint for the short-, intermediate, and long-term experimental groups. Triplicate 1 L bottles spiked with *P. marinus* were sampled for each Abiotic timepoint. Figure by Claire Garfield and Erin Maybach.

Table 8. Total number of samples taken during incubation experiments at BATS and LTER sites.

Parameter	# Samples BATS	# Samples LTER	Responsible lab
MetaG	9	9	Dyhrman
MetaT	15	15	Moran
FCM	93	87	Moran
RSG	35	0	Moran

Metabolites	111	99	Kujawinski
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Preliminary Results:

Figure 15. Average cell counts ($n = 3$) and standard deviation for the BATS incubation experiment. Squares indicate *M. commoda* DOC treatments, circles *Prochlorococcus*, and triangles are T0 bulk samples off the CTD. Figure created by Claire Garfield.

Incubations: Oxygen utilization and respiration of metabolites

Rachel Sandquist, Carlson Lab – UCSB

Experimental goal:

The goal of these remineralization bioassays was to investigate the relationship between the amount of oxygen utilized by native heterotrophic bacterioplankton during the remineralization of the amended phytoplankton exometabolites to help constrain variability observed in naturally occurring respiratory quotients (RQ). By conducting these experiments at both the BATS and LTER site we were able to investigate both how the different exometabolite compositions drive variability in RQ and also how the water chemistry (temperature and nutrients) and heterotrophic community composition may also drive variability. By running this experiment in parallel to the incubation experiments, we hope to use gene expression data to help inform what specific metabolic pathways are being utilized by the heterotrophic microbes when they encounter the exometabolites.

Two remineralization bioassays were conducted, one at the BATS site which ran for about 6 days and the other at the LTER site and ran for about 3 days. Oxygen was monitored continuously throughout both experiments while bacterial abundance, organic carbon drawdown, DNA, inorganic nutrients, and metabolites incubations were run in parallel and sampled at set intervals.

Experimental setup:

A total of 25 liters of seawater were collected from 15 m depth for the remineralization experiments (Figure 16). Seawater was collected in the morning from the same cast as the incubation experiments (1000 hours at BATS; 0500 hours at LTER). 70% of the seawater was collected as the seawater media by directly filtering it through a rinsed, 0.2 μm PES filter from the Niskin to remove the bacterial communities. Due to the high amount of particles in the water at the LTER site, the media was inline filtered through a rinsed 3.0 μm PES filter and a rinsed 0.2 μm PES filter. 30% of the seawater was collected as whole, unfiltered water as the inoculum with the natural ambient microbial community. The dilution of the seawater before the amendment of the carbon treatments allows space for the heterotrophic bacteria to grow upon utilization of the amended carbon as well as a dilution of grazing pressure (and grazer respiration) on the bacteria. The media and inoculum were collected and mixed in a 50 L carboy and then dispersed into three 8L carboys which were acid washed and milli Q rinsed before the experiment as well as triple rinsed with seawater mixture upon set up. Once filled to 8L, 1.6 mL of *P. marinus* and *M. commoda* mix (each) were amended to their respective carboys, mixed, and allowed to sit for 45 minutes before parallel filling began.

Figure 16. Experimental setup and sampling timeline for the phytoplankton exometabolite remineralization experiments. Figure created by Rachel Sandquist.

After 45 minutes, parallel incubations were filled in the order: biological oxygen demand (BOD) bottles, total organic carbon vials, and then 2L polycarbonate bottles whereby all the BOD bottles

were filled and put in the incubator set at in situ temperature of 20 °C, followed by all the total organic carbon, and then all the biotainers.

To fill the BOD bottles, clean tubing was connected to each 8L carboy with the tubing in the bottom of each BOD bottle. Each bottle was then filled, allowing it to overflow three times and rotating to allow the release of any bubbles. The tubing was then slowly removed while still overflowing the BOD bottle to ensure no bubbles were in the bottle. The BOD bottles were immediately airtight closed with a glass plug and turned to tighten without the introduction of any bubbles. The outsides of the BOD bottles were rinsed off with Milli Q and wiped with a kimwipe to remove any saltwater taking extra care to make sure the optode was clear. The tops of the BOD bottles were then filled with MilliQ. Three samples were selected to be killed with 250 µL HgCl₂ and act as the killed controls. All bottles were immediately moved back to the incubator to bring to temperature as the rest of the experiment was set up. Next 15 pre-combusted 40 mL borosilicate vials were filled for each treatment for the total organic parallels. Care was taken not to introduce organic contamination to the vials by triple rinsing each vial before filling directly from the 8L spigot. After filling, the vials were immediately placed in the same incubator as the BOD bottles. Finally, two 2L polycarbonate biotainers were triple rinsed and filled with the remaining water in the 8L carboys. Once filled, the biotainers were placed in the incubator and T0 sampling began.

T0 and the subsequent sampling was conducted as follows for each parameter:

- Total Organic Carbon: triplicates were fixed for each treatment at each designated TOC timepoint with 60 µL of 4N HCl to a pH < 2.
- Bacterial Abundance: 1 mL duplicates were sampled into 2mL cryovials from each biotainer (2 x biotainer 4x treatment) were fixed at each designated BA time point with 25 µL 6% paraformaldehyde for a final concentration of 0.16%. The samples were inverted and incubated at 4 °C for 20 minutes before being frozen at -80 °C
- Metabolites: triplicate samples were taken at the initial and final timepoints from each biotainer. 30 mL of samples were filtered through 0.2µm PTFE filters into 40 mL borosilicate vials. *M. commoda* and the control samples shared a filter and *P. marinus* used its own filter to avoid any potential carryover contamination from a clogged filter.
- Nutrients: single samples were taken from each biotainer into clean HDPE bottles (1 x biotainer 2x treatment) at each designated nutrients timepoint. Samples were taken without gloves to avoid nitrogen contamination and immediately frozen at -20°C.
- DNA: single samples were taken at the initial and final time point from each biotainer. Sample volume was filtered through a 47mm 0.2µm Supor filter (500 mL each at T0 and 1.5L each at TF). Filters were stored in 5mL cryovials and immediately frozen.

Post Cruise Sample Plan

Table 9. Total number of samples taken during remineralization experiments at BATS and LTER sites.

Parameter	# Samples BATS	# Samples LTER	Lab for Analysis
TOC	45	45	Carlson
FCM	72	48	Carlson
MetaG	12	12	Carlson
Nuts	30	18	Carlson
Metabolites	36	36	Kujawinski
Oxygen	~ 620	~ 303	Carlson

BATS Exometabolite Remineralization Experiment Organic Carbon and Oxygen Trends

Figure 17. Preliminary results from the remineralization experiment at BATS showing drawdown of oxygen and organic carbon. Interesting trends show the drawdown of carbon in the *P. marinus* exometabolite amendment along with an increased oxygen utilization as opposed to minimal carbon and oxygen drawdown in the control and *M. commoda* exometabolite amendment. Though minimal, it is interesting to see oxygen utilization in the absence of carbon removal in the control and *M. commoda* exometabolite amendment as well. Figure provided by Rachel Sandquist.

Biological differences between stations

Phytoplankton identification: PlanktoScope

We used a PlanktoScope V2.6 (<https://www.fairscope.com/>) to visualize microbes in the ~50-300 μm size range. The goal was to trial using this instrument to identify and quantify microbes based on image and morphological characteristics. Samples were collected from the underway system or by net tow using a small 52 μm net when possible. After sample collection, cells were imaged on the Planktoscope using a 300 μm flow cell.

Due to the rocking motion of the ship (especially during the storms), we could not consistently and effectively do automated imaging. That is, the fluidics were often disrupted by ship movement and automatic imaging yielded mostly blurry images. We resorted to doing mostly manual 'exploratory' imaging as a result. We were also unable to quantify the amount of water that was filtered through the net, and only sampled when time permitted. Altogether, these hurdles meant that PlanktoScope sampling on this cruise could only be used for qualitative purposes. Loay will continue analyzing the image data to provide some qualitative insights about community composition. In the future, more dedicated and consistent sampling could yield better quantitative measurements.

Overall, we observed dinoflagellates and small diatoms at BATS (and during the oligotrophic sections of the transit) and very high abundance of *Coscinodiscus sp.* at and near LTER. Figure 18 shows some of the images collected and Figure 19 displays images of plankton collected along the cruise track.

Figure 18. Top: PlanktoScope images of various types of dinoflagellates. Bottom: PlanktoScope images of *Coscinodiscus sp.* diatoms at LTER. Figure by Loay Jabre.

Figure 19. Images of plankton collected using the Planktoscope along the AE2504 cruise track. Sampling locations are represented by circles on the map and color indicates sea surface temperature at the time of collection. Figure by Loay Jabre.

Protease activity with depth

Fadime Stemmer, Saito Lab - MIT/WHOI

Experimental goal

Proteins constitute a major component of the surface organic matter pool. Their breakdown and recycling are important factors in the attenuation of carbon flux into the deep, i.e., the biological pump, and thus play a significant role in carbon cycling and sequestration. Heterotrophic microorganisms encode a variety of proteases to break down proteinaceous organic matter in the surface and upper mesopelagic ocean, some of which are secreted into the ambient seawater. Despite their importance in carbon cycling, their activity and the contribution to the upper ocean carbon flux has not been described. This experiment aims at determining the bulk protease activity in ambient seawater across different depths.

Methods

Samples were collected from filters both underway (sampling from sea surface at ~2 m) and from the CLIO AUV (Table 10). Details on samples and associated metadata is recorded in the proteaseactivity_metadata.txt file.

Sample collection ID	# Samples BATS	# Samples LTER	# Samples Transit
clio051	16	/	/
clio052	16	/	/
clio054	/	16	/
UW	1	/	28

Table 10. Total number of samples taken for protease assay experiments at BATS and LTER sites.

Sample collection

Seawater from the underway system was filtered through 142 mm Versapor filters (51 μm), followed by 142 mm Versapor filters (0.2 μm). The flow was stopped after approximately 40 minutes. Details on the underway sampling can be found in section “*Large-volume sampling: Underway Sampling*”. At the beginning of each sampling step, sterile filtered seawater from the station was collected in 15 ml sampling tubes for background determination and sample dilution.

Seawater was filtered on CLIO through 142 mm Versapor filters (51 μm , 0.2 μm) as described in “*Large-volume sampling: CLIO*”. Sterile filtered seawater from each depth was collected in 15 ml falcon tubes from the clamshell filter head and utilized for background correction and sample dilution.

Sample preparation

Filters were carefully removed from the filter head, cut to 1/8 filter slices and transferred to a sterile 15 ml falcon tube. To each sample tube, 2 ml of the respective seawater filtrate were added, and the tubes shaken to resuspend loose biomass. Using clean pincers the filter was removed, placed on a clean surface and residual biomass scratched off the filter with an inoculation loop. The filter and loop were placed back into the falcon tube and the tube shaken to resuspend the remaining biomass. Samples were stored at 4°C until taken for protease assay sampling (max. 8 hours from sampling to measurement).

Protease Assay

The Pierce™ Fluorescent Protease Assay Kit (Thermo Scientific) was used for fluorometric protease activity determination. Of each resuspended sample, triplicates of 50 μl were diluted in a black, flat-bottom 96-well plate to a final volume of 200 μl with 0.5 μM , 1 μM , 2 μM and 3 μM of FTC-labelled casein in digestion buffer (25 mM Tris, 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.2). For samples from the CLIO dive 051, control runs with addition of 1 mM AEBSF serine protease inhibitor were conducted. Control runs for the other dives will be conducted with samples stored at -20°C in the following weeks. The reaction was monitored on a Spectramax M3 spectrophotometer, measuring fluorescence every 30 seconds over the course of 4 or 8 hours at $\lambda_{\text{exc./em.}}=485/538$ nm and 25°C. The data was processed and analyzed using a python workflow. In summary, samples were corrected by the respective media blank which was measured in triplicate and averaged before subtraction. The data was normalized against the first datapoint in the dataframe. A polynomial fit of 9th degree ($R^2 \geq 0.90$) was fitted

against the normalized fluorescence vs. time curves, and the initial bulk proteolysis rate determined, i.e., the rate at the beginning of the experiment (time = 0, t_0), where protease activity is not limited by substrate availability. The degree of the fit was chosen based on how well the fit represented the curves without oversimplification or overfitting. The standard errors of the initial rates were determined through bootstrap resampling ($n=10,000$). The proteolysis rates (PR) were converted from fluorescence intensity per minute ($FI \text{ min}^{-1}$) to units of fmol fluorescent substrate overturned per minute (fmol min^{-1}) using an empirically determined conversion factor of 2.5 fmol FI^{-1} across samples was identified empirically. The maximal proteolysis rates (v_{\max}) and half-saturation constant (K_m) were determined using the Michaelis Menten kinetic model (Equation 1) transformed into the double-reciprocal Lineweaver-Burk representation (Equation 2), where v is the proteolysis rate at a given substrate concentration, and $[FITC]$ is the concentration of the fluorometric substrate FITC-casein.

$$v = (v_{\max} * [FITC]) / (K_m + [FITC]) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$1/v = (K_m/v_{\max}) * (1/[FITC]) + (1/v_{\max}) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Figure 20. Protocol for protease activity sample preparation and measurement. Filters were obtained from Underway or CLIO sampling. The filters were extracted and cut to $\frac{1}{8}$ of the original filter size. The biomass was resuspended in sterile filtered seawater and the sample used in a fluorometric protease activity assay. Figure created in Bio Render by Fadime Stemmer.

Results

Fluorescence intensity was plotted against time for each clio and underway protease activity sample and can be found saved on the GitHub repository of this project. Control measurements with addition of 1 mM AEBSF Serine protease inhibitor were conducted for samples from clio dive 051. The protease activity was clearly inhibited by protease inhibitor addition, suggesting that the increase in fluorescence was due to proteolytic digestion rather than unspecific cleavage or bleaching of the fluorescent dye. Samples taken at BATS showed higher activities and more turnover

of the fluorescent dye in the 0.2 μm fraction across all depths, while at LTER, higher protease activity was observed in the 51 μm fraction for samples from 15, 30, 40, 50, and 60 m depth.

The maximal proteolysis rates were computed using both Michaelis Menten and Lineweaver burk fits to the initial rate extracted from the raw fluorescence data. However, substrate saturation was not reached in most samples causing large errors and unreasonable data for both fits. Instead, the initial protease activity (at time $t=0$ min) was determined for each depth of the three successful CLIO dives (Figure 21 A, B, C), as well as for underway samples during transit between BATS and LTER measured at the highest sampled FTC-casein concentration of 3 μM (Figure 22). This fluorescent substrate concentration was used since it is closest to the substrate saturation condition among the conditions tested.

Depth profiles of protease activity from CLIO dives

BATS samples are represented in clio dives 051 and 052. At clio051, the 0.2 μm size fraction was significantly and consistently higher than the 51 μm fraction (Figure 21A). Except for the deeper surface ocean (60-120 m), no activity could be determined in the 51 μm samples. For the 0.2 μm samples, protease activity decreased slightly up to a depth of 45 m, and then increased going deeper in the water column. The highest activity was observed in the 0.2 μm fraction at 90 m depth with $4.15 \pm 0.83 \text{ fmol min}^{-1}$, before decreasing to $2.35 \text{ fmol min}^{-1}$ at 120 m. The same trend was observed in the 0.2 μm size fraction for clio dive 052 (Figure 21B), however the activity rose even higher to up to $6.65 \pm 0.88 \text{ fmol min}^{-1}$ at 90 m depth. Surprisingly, there was protease activity across all depths determined for 51 μm filtered samples of this dive. While the trend was opposite to the trend observed in the 0.2 μm size fraction, the rate peaked at 90 m reaching the same activity on both filters. For both clio051 and clio052, the chlorophyll-A concentration drastically decreased at a depth of 70 m to 80 m, just above the peak in protease activity (Figures 2 and 6 of CLIO Dive report). This would suggest that the majority of the protease activity did not result from phytoplankton but rather stems from heterotrophic bacteria that feed on sinking phytoplankton organic matter by releasing proteases into the ambient seawater. The small size of the cells in the oligotrophic ocean and thus their slow sinking rate could explain the observation that the proteolytic activity peaks below the deep chlorophyll maximum. This is corroborated by the observation of a slight drop in the oxygen concentration at approximately 80 to 100 m from 250 μM to 230 μM .

The rates in the mesopelagic samples (500 m, 1000 m, 1500 m) were lower than in the surface ocean. While there was a dip in activity at 1000 m in the 0.2 μm size fraction, the activity peaked in the 51 μm size fraction.

Proteolysis rates determined at LTER were significantly higher in the 51 μm size fraction across the surface ocean, increasing consistently up to $30.2 \pm 2.63 \text{ fmol min}^{-1}$ at a depth of 50 m, before falling drastically to $1.63 \pm 1.43 \text{ fmol min}^{-1}$ at 100 m depth (Figure 21C). This is in line with the observation of a big *Coscinodiscus* bloom at LTER. Probably, proteolytic activity is high due to the large amount of sinking *Coscinodiscus* cells, which could either produce their own secreted proteases or could be colonized by heterotrophic bacteria or archaea that take advantage of sinking particles as high nutrient environments. These can be exploited for amino acids and other organic carbon and nitrogen sources. The 0.2 μm fraction is similar to the samples at BATS, in that there is a slight decrease in activity up to 40 m before the proteolysis rates increase with depth up to 80 m and finally decrease at 100 m. The range of activity is also similar to the observations made at BATS.

Figure 21. Initial bulk protease activity (V_0 in fmol min^{-1}) from *Clio* dives **A, *clio051* (BATS); **B**, *clio052* (BATS); **C**, *clio054* (LTER). Rates were determined from samples measured at a FITC casein concentration of $3 \mu\text{M}$. Measurements were made at 25°C . Purple: $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ filter, Blue: $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ filter + 1mM serine protease inhibitor (PI), Green: $51 \mu\text{m}$ filter, Yellow: $51 \mu\text{m}$ filter + 1mM serine protease inhibitor. Figure created by Fadime Stemmer.**

Surface transect of protease activity measured from BATS to LTER

Protease activity measurements were made from underway sampling during transect from BATS (UW28) to LTER (UW107). Sampling locations are highlighted in Figure 22A. The protease activity from the initial section of the fluorescence curve for a substrate concentration of 3 μM is displayed in Figure 22B. Protease activity in the 0.2 μm fraction increases strongly between station UW28 and UW70. Those two samples were taken four days apart and at different times of day - 1600 and 2100 respectively, which could have affected the protease activity. The proteolytic activity increased on the transect up to UW77. There is a slight decrease in activity until UW 89, another peak at UW93, followed by a strong decrease in activity for UW96. The protease activity in the 51 μm fraction is high at BATS and decreases as we drew closer to LTER, with the exception of UW73.

Figure 22. Underway Protease Activity Sampling. **A**, Sampling locations for protease activity assays during underway sampling. **B**, Initial bulk protease activity (in fmol min^{-1}) from Underway samples during Transit from BATS to LTER measured at a FITC casein concentration of 3 μM . Figure created by Fadime Stemmer.

The last three samples (UW 99, 103, and 107) are across the continental shelf break which is characterized by a strong decrease in sea surface temperature. Moreover, the chlorophyll

concentration in the surface seawater increased significantly between UW96 and UW99, as well as UW99 and UW103. While the protease activity in the 0.2 μm size fraction increases from 6.38 ± 0.95 to 6.90 ± 1.00 fmol min^{-1} , barely any activity was detected for the last three 51 μm samples. As we reached the continental shelf break, nutrient rich cold waters were replacing nutrient depleted waters, causing a spring bloom of *Coscinodiscus* in the North Atlantic Shelf. These large diatoms quickly sink which could explain why the protease activity in the 51 μm size fraction was noticeably lower than in the 21 μm fraction in the top 2 m of the water column. The dip in protease activity at UW96 correlates well with lower chlorophyll content compared to UW93 and UW99, as well as a strong increase in sea surface temperature.

In the following weeks, protease assays with protease inhibitor addition will be conducted for clio052, clio054 and all underway samples. Moreover, the determined rates will be normalized with relative protein abundance determined from metaproteomics conducted on the clio and underway filters in order to better understand the cellular contributions to bulk proteolytic activity. Metaproteomics will further allow us to determine which proteases were produced and potentially involved in the observed activities.

Of sterile filtered seawater 15 ml were collected for all depths and locations and stored at -80°C . In the upcoming weeks, these samples will be analysed using a novel MS-based protease activity assay, which will allow us to investigate the cell-free, secreted proteolytic potential in ambient seawater, without biases introduced by pre-concentration steps and the difficulty of reaching substrate saturation.

Phytoplankton and virus isolation

The overwhelming majority of marine eukaryotic viruses identified by meta-omics have yet to be isolated in culture. The goal of this effort was to collect samples for downstream isolation of novel eukaryotic virus-host pairs. Viruses are obligate parasites, so having a susceptible host in culture is required for virus isolation. Representative eukaryotic phytoplankton strains from oligotrophic (BATS) and coastal (NES-LTER) sites will be isolated to serve as bait strains for virus isolation.

Three full-scale isolation efforts were performed, one at BATS and two at the LTER. 20L of whole seawater was collected from 15m and serially filtered through 20 μm , 5 μm , and 0.8 μm membrane filters and an 0.2 μm Sterivex unit with three parallel lines. The water was prefiltered through 200 μm mesh, with the exception of the second LTER sampling in which the mesh was excluded to enhance recovery of large diatoms (Figure 23).

The 20 μm , 5 μm , and 0.8 μm membrane filters were resuspended in 20 ml of sterile artificial seawater (ASW). All three filters of the same size were combined into a single resuspension, resulting in a 1000X concentration of each size fraction. The 20mm resuspension was aliquoted into 4 12-well microplates which contained L1/5 or L1/20 (BATS) or L1 or L1/5 (LTER). The 5 μm and 0.8 μm resuspensions were each aliquoted into 2 12-well microplates which contained L1/5 or L1/20 (BATS) or L1 or L1/5 (LTER). All three resuspensions were each also streaked onto 3 L1+agar plates. Microplates and agar plates were incubated at 16°C under a 12:12 light:dark cycle for the duration of the cruise. Upon return, the samples were moved to 18°C (BATS) or 15°C (LTER) incubators. As of April 7th, I have observed growth in many of the samples from both sites and have transferred these

samples into new media (Figure 24). The next steps will move toward single cell isolation via cell picking and dilution to extinction.

Concentration of viral size fractions is commonly employed in marine environments to enhance virus isolation efforts (Suttle et al 1991). Giant viruses (*Nucleocytoviricota* > 0.2 μ m) were concentrated by collecting the 0.8 μ m filtrate on a Sterivex unit. The three filters were resuspended in 10ml of ASW, resulting in a 2000X concentration. The resuspensions were stored at 4°C for the duration of the cruise. Viruses smaller than 0.2 μ m were concentrated via tangential flow filtration using Vivaflow cassettes with a molecular weight cutoff of 50kDa. Concentration factors varied, but ranged from 100-600X. The concentrates were stored at 4°C for the duration of the cruise. In addition to the full-scale isolation samples, 0.2 μ m filtered water was collected from the underway and the LTER diel experiment at varying time points (Table 11). Immediate plans for virus isolation from concentrates involve screening previously isolated phytoplankton strains, predominantly diatoms, for lysis after addition of the concentrates. Future efforts will involve similar screening of novel phytoplankton isolates.

Table 11. Samples collected for phytoplankton and virus isolation

Site	Cast #	Time	Type	Volume collected	Virus concentrate	0.2 μ m resuspension	20 μ m culture	5 μ m culture	0.8 μ m culture
BATS	13	10:00	Virus concentration	10L	N/A	X			
BATS	43	9:30	Full	20L	113X, 125 ml	X	X	X	X
BATS	43	9:30	Virus concentration	15L	600X, 25ml				
Intermediate /underway	3/16 16:00 underway	16:00	Virus concentration	11L	220X, 50ml				
LTER	45	2:00	Full	20L	166X, 120ml	X	X	X	X
LTER	51	22:00	Virus concentration	8L	178X, 45ml				
LTER	59	6:00	Full	10L	220X, 45ml	X	X	X	X
LTER	63	10:00	Virus concentration	7.75L	127X, 61ml				

Figure 23. Phytoplankton isolation and virus concentration workflow. Figure created by Annika Gomez.

Figure 24. A. Pennate diatoms from BATS grown in L/5, 200X magnification B. Mixed culture from BATS grown in L1/5, 400X magnification C. Mixed culture from LTER grown in L1,200X magnification D. Coccolithophores from LTER grown in L1, 200X magnification. Figure by Annika Gomez.

Bacterioplankton isolation

This project aims to isolate and characterize bacterioplankton from different ocean depths using CLIO filters collected during the AE2504 cruise in the TIGERCLAW Bay. This work contributes to understanding microbial diversity across depth gradients and supports downstream identification and functional characterization of novel marine bacteria.

Seawater collected using CLIO dives was filtered through 0.2 μm filters at various depths. Each filter was then used to streak marine agar plates to isolate bacterioplankton. Plates were incubated at 4 degrees Celsius, and growth was monitored over time. The colonies that emerged are now being isolated in liquid marine broth to increase biomass. The next step is to perform protein extractions and identify the bacterial isolates through proteomic methods.

Samples Collected:

Total plates prepared: 26

Depth range: 5 m to 1500 m

Collection site: TIGERCLAW Bay

CLIO dives: clio051, clio052, clio053, clio054

Notable depths include:

Shallow: 5 m, 15 m, 20 m, 30 m, 35 m

Mid-depth: 60 m, 75 m, 100 m, 250 m, 500 m

Deep: 1000 m, 1500 m

Preliminary Observations:

Of the 26 total plates, 21 showed visible colony growth as of April 9, 2025. Notably, viable bacterioplankton were recovered from a wide range of depths, including the deepest (1500 m) and the shallowest (5 m), with particularly rich growth observed in mid-depth stations (e.g., 250–1000 m). This suggests a diverse and abundant bacterioplankton community throughout the water column in TIGERCLAW Bay. Plates from certain depths (e.g., 120 m, 75 m, 60 m) did not show growth, which may point to localized environmental differences or differences in initial microbial abundance.

Next Steps:

Isolates from plates with colony growth are currently being transferred to liquid marine broth cultures to increase biomass. Protein extractions will follow, to identify bacterial taxa using proteomics and/or molecular techniques like 16S rRNA sequencing. These analyses will take place at WHOI and may involve collaboration with C-CoMP and associated labs for further characterization and data integration.

Figure 25. Photos of bacteria growing on plates from 1000m (left), 1500m (middle), and 500m (right). Figure by Daniella Asturias.

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CLIO Operations on AE2504-SE

CLIO OPERATIONS ON
AE2504-SE, CHIEF SCIENTIST E. KUJAWINSKI

WHOI Clio Operations Group
Michael Jakuba Chip Breier

Clio Expedition Leader: Michael Jakuba

R/V Atlantic Explorer — 2025-03-09 through 2025-03-23

Publication Date: March 22, 2025

1 Summary

This document summarizes operations with the *Clio* AUV during AE2504-SE, Chief Scientist E. Kujawinski. Included in this report are records of the vehicle configuration, basic vehicle and sensor performance, and post-dive reports. This report does not attempt to describe any scientific results or conclusions. The individual dive summaries for *Clio* dives 051-054 follows, each of which is a free-standing document summarizing the dive.

2 Cruise Log

This section provides a brief chronological summary of *Clio* activities during the cruise. Additional information on specific dives is available in the dive reports.

2025-03-06 *Clio* group arrives at BIOS and begins mobe.

2023-03-09 Depart BIOS, Bermuda.

2023-03-10 clio051 aborted at launch.

2023-03-11 Weather.

2023-03-12 Weather.

2023-03-13 clio051 at BATS.

2023-03-14 clio052 at BATS.

2023-03-15 Transit to NES LTER.

2023-03-16 Transit to NES LTER.

2023-03-17 Weather.

2023-03-18 Weather.

2023-03-19 clio053 at NES LTER.

2023-03-20 clio054 at NES LTER.

2023-03-21 Transit to WHOI (weather); arrive at WHOI

2023-03-22 Demobe at WHOI.

3 Ship Specific Information

This section summarizes ship specific information and is primarily intended to facilitate more effective use of the same vessel in the future.

S.1: A-Frame used for Clio operations

S.2: Clio strapped midships on fantail. Cableway from crane pedestal to lifting bale topper.

S.3: Micromodem and 10 kHz towfish used to listen on dives opportunistically.

S.4: Clio topside installed in fwd/port corner of aft port-side lab. Forward 02 deck lab van used for some storage. Two empty pallet boxes strapped down on port side of fantail.

Clio 051 Dive Report

Michael Jakuba Chip Breier

Clio Expedition Leader: Michael Jakuba

Summary

clio051 was an upper water-column sampling dive. All samples were collected at constant depth (isobaric).

Weather: Fair with light winds and moderate swell.

Reason for end of dive: End of planned mission.

Dive Statistics

Launch: 2025-03-13 12:46:46 UTC

On surface: 2025-03-13 20:05:36 UTC

Recovery: 2025-03-13 20:26:28 UTC

Maximum depth: 120.0 m

Surface-to-surface dive time: 07:39:42

Payload Sensors

- Bushbaby SUPR (pump not functional)
- Tigerclaw SUPR
- Aanderaa 4831FDW optode
- SBE SeaCAT49 CTD
- SBE DEEPSUNA V2 nitrate analyzer (out of calibration, see post-dive notes)
- SBE C-Star transmissometer
- WetLabs FLUNTRTD fluorometer (Chl-a/Turbidity)

Figure 1: clio051: Tigerclaw SUPR sampling history, valve and volume pumped versus depth station.

Figure 2: clio051: profile sensor data, whole dive.

Figure 3: clio051: profile sensor data versus time, whole dive.

Figure 4: clio051: Control system performance.

Post dive notes

one weight dropped off at about 19:20 UTC, this is on the final two 15 m holds. 25 N = 2.5 kg = 5#. See no evidence of the other one falling off while sampling. Could be obscured by an ascent. Could also have fallen off during surface interval prior to recovery.

143 N at 120 m when almost certainly both weights were still on.

batt charge reported was 55% at end of dive. This is completely bogus. Batts were already on the sharply decreasing part of the discharge curve, cells at about 3.2 V is a good threshold for immediate stoppage and probably a passive float up. 3.4 V is the start of the steep discharge. $3.2 \times 16 = 51.2$ V $3.4 \times 16 = 54.4$ V do not know status, but dive should abort on V at 54 V. Ideally there would be two thresholds... Not implemented, but requires only the logic in mx and then to test. Everything else is shelled out and ready.

052 is a longer dive. Need to make ballast tighter.

SUNA is out of calibration. The relative changes in uM look probably ok, but the absolute value is negative during the dive. 2025/03/14 13:52:21 running with DI water in the thing on deck. Stable about -7.5 after getting bubbles out, I think, but this is probably not a great cal. If -7.5 is true, then the data from 051 (-7 typ.) would indicate oligotropic conditions with somewhat higher conc deeper. This deck cal data is in a clio052.?? log. 2025/03/14 15:04:30 drained DI water. was stable at -6.7, dipped to -23, then stabilized after a few minutes to -9.6.

clio051 was first attempted 2025-03-10. The dive was aborted at launch prior to slipping the main taglines when the thrusters did not spin upon entering the water (this indicates mission-start). The issue was traced to high atmospheric pressure requiring a larger than usual "min depth" of 1.4 m to trigger mission start. The associated variable is a signed byte with a maximum value of 127 (1.27 m). When operators entered 1.4 m, the resultant value rolled over to less than zero, defeating the logic used to prevent the thrusters from spinning on deck. Insufficient time with favorable weather remained to re-attempt the launch.

Clio 052 Dive Report

Michael Jakuba Chip Breier

Clio Expedition Leader: Michael Jakuba

Summary

clio052 was an upper water-column sampling dive. All samples were collected at constant depth (isobaric).

Weather: Fair with moderate winds and swell.

Reason for end of dive: End of planned mission.

Dive Statistics

Launch: 3/14/2025 16:36, 32° 6.18042' N, 63° 37.44348' W

On surface: 3/15/2025 02:53 UTC, 32° 5.75670' N 63° 34.96494' W

Maximum depth: 1500.0 m

Surface-to-surface dive time: 11h 27m

Payload Sensors

- Bushbaby SUPR (pump not functional)
- Tigerclaw SUPR
- Aanderaa 4831FDW optode
- SBE SeaCAT49 CTD
- SBE DEEPSUNA V2 nitrate analyzer (out of calibration)
- SBE C-Star transmissometer
- WetLabs FLUNTRTD fluorometer (Chl-a/Turbidity)

Figure 6: clio052: profile sensor data, initial downcast only.

Figure 7: clio052: profile sensor data versus time, whole dive.

Figure 8: clio052: Control system performance.

Post dive notes

elm1 failed at 16:37 UTC during descent. SV was drained of oil but it was possible to reenable it and it spun. PV seems fine, but on the GUI, PV was the one reporting a hall fault 0x04. s/w seems to be consistent wrt numbering etc, but cables may be reversed? vehicle did not break stride. small blip in vertical speed, but otherwise continued dive. computed forces are all obviously wrong.

Batts again down to about 3.45 V per cell. Good thing that drop weight was added. minimum reported thrust was 148 N (at 500 m), but this is post-thruster failure, so actual thrust applied was 74 N. Was the drop weight on or off? Weight clearly fell off at 01:21 UTC. 4.7# nominal.

spreadsheet predicted -4.4 kgf at surface exclusive of air bags with all three 5# ballast weights in place. At 500 m seeing 74 N (7.6 kg). So underestimating buoyancy by 2.5 to 3 kg. Pretty big error. similar underestimate on 051.

Induced roll was 3 deg holding, 4 deg transiting down at 0.5 m/s. up thrust was close to zero, so no roll induced.

Cu dropweights: 4 diameter by 1 thick would be about 5#. McM: \$105 ea. What about wax-coating steel? Cu so expensive. SS \$63 for same disk. Still expensive, and all would need a hole drilled too. \$30 for lead-antimony alloy uncoated 5# dive weight.

Also could just use slower releases so that weights come back... Headed N for rest of this cruise so rot will be slower.

Unplugged Batt1/stbd Thruster cable (as labeled) at housing. According to GUI, PV enables, SV does not. upon trying to spin, both errored out with 0x40. Plug back in B1/Stbd; unplug B2/Port. According to GUI, SV enables, PV does not. Physically the SV prop is spinning. This is the thruster that has lost most/all? of its comp oil. Surprise! Both thrusters need to be replaced. Software and cable labels are all correct.

Definitely something mechanically wrong with PV. Much higher friction than usual, though feels viscous. does enable sometimes and spins fine, at usual speed, and doesn't sound any worse. Replace regardless.

rm NHT-03 - comp low/maybe empty. Was SV for clio051/052. No faults. rm NHT-05 - no obvious issues outside, but faults 0x40 (hall) occasionally (happened subsea, and several times on deck per testing above).

installed NHT-01 on SV; NHT-02 on PV. passed deck test.

Clio 053 Dive Report

Michael Jakuba Chip Breier

Clio Expedition Leader: Michael Jakuba

Summary

clio053 was an upper water-column sampling dive.
All samples were collected at constant depth (isobaric).
Weather: Fog with moderate winds and swell.
Reason for end of dive: End of planned mission.

Dive Statistics

Launch: 3/19/2025 13:06 UTC, 39° 43.12716' N -70° 57.50190' W
On surface: 3/20/2025 00:21 UTC, 39° 40.76574' N -71° 3.24288' W
Maximum depth: 1000 m
Surface-to-surface dive time: 12h 45min

Payload Sensors

- Bushbaby SUPR
- Tigerclaw SUPR
- Aanderaa 4831FDW optode
- SBE SeaCAT49 CTD
- SBE DEEPSUNA V2 nitrate analyzer (out of calibration)
- SBE C-Star transmissometer
- WetLabs FLUNTRTD fluorometer (Chl-a/Turbidity)

Figure 9: clio053: Bushbaby SUPR sampling history, valve and volume pumped versus depth station.

Figure 10: clio053: Tigerclaw SUPR sampling history, valve and volume pumped versus depth station.

Figure 11: clio053: Profiling sensor data, initial downcast only.

Figure 12: clio053: Profiling sensor data vs. time, whole dive.

Figure 13: clio053: Control system performance.

Post dive notes

Mission held as normal but resumed - this is because we re-dunked it and forgot to remove safety line. It correctly went to the end of the mission.

Mission plan looks like it had an error, valve 15 on TC was used for a filter, but it was connected to the incubator chamber.

Bushbaby SUPR had problems. After first two samples, supr activity never made it to 3 (pump fwd). but was stuck at (2) (rotating valve initial)

reason for delayed surfacing was timeout on valve move initial. These happened only after the 100 m sample. Looks like it's a 1 minute penalty for each sample where the valve did not turn. That's not enough to explain 25 min.

Clio 054 Dive Report

Michael Jakuba Chip Breier

Clio Expedition Leader: Michael Jakuba

Summary

clio054 was an upper water-column sampling dive and included an engineering test of roll control. All samples were collected at constant depth (isobaric).

Weather: Fair with light winds and long period swell.

Reason for end of dive: End of planned mission.

Dive Statistics

Launch: 2025-03-20 16:10 UTC, 39° 41.45106' N -71° 13.01052' W

On surface: 2025-03-20 22:42 UTC, 39° 41.35326' N -71° 16.19946' W

Maximum depth: 300 m

Surface-to-surface dive time: 06:32

Payload Sensors

- Bushbaby SUPR (ballast only)
- Tigerclaw SUPR
- Aanderaa 4831FDW optode
- SBE SeaCAT49 CTD
- SBE DEEPSUNA V2 nitrate analyzer (out of calibration)
- SBE C-Star transmissometer
- WetLabs FLUNTRTD fluorometer (Chl-a/Turbidity)

Figure 14: clio054: Tigerclaw SUPR sampling history, valve and volume pumped versus depth station.

Figure 15: clio054: Profiling sensor data, initial downcast only.

Figure 16: clio054: Profiling sensor data vs. time, whole dive.

Figure 17: clio054: Control system performance.

Post dive notes

There was confusion about Clio's schedule during the dive. It appeared late relative to the dive planning spreadsheet. The final update to the spreadsheet was not reflected in the mission loaded. Clio ran one earlier iteration of the plan. The dive planning spreadsheet was updated to the actual mission plan flow.